

ELASTIC WAVE PROPAGATION INDUCED BY PIEZOELECTRIC ACTUATORS FOR HEALTH MONITORING OF STRUCTURES

Xiaodong Wang and Guoliang Huang
Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Alberta
Edmonton, Alberta, Canada T6G 2G8
email: xiaodong.wang@ualberta.ca

SUMMARY Piezoelectric actuator-induced wave propagation is now being considered for use in health monitoring of structures. The current study provides a comprehensive analysis of the elastic wave propagation generated by surface bonded and embedded thin-sheet piezoelectric actuators. A one-dimensional actuator model is used to simulate the actuation process and the dynamic load transfer between the actuators and the host medium. The resulting wave propagation due to multiple actuators is determined using a Pseudo-incident wave method. Detailed numerical simulation is conducted to study the electroelastic behaviour of this composite system.

KEYWORDS : Wave propagation, Actuator, Smart Structures, Health monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric actuators and sensors are being integrated with conventional structural element to form intelligent systems [1-2]. Recent developments in exploring this technology include active noise control and vibration suppression of structures, position control of flexible robot arms, smart skin systems for submarines and shape control of advanced structures [3-6]. Due to the presence of the material discontinuity between the actuators and the host medium, a complicated stress field is generated when external electric fields are applied to the actuators. It is difficult to simulate this actuation process using analytical solutions based on the original boundary/interface conditions. As the result, simplified actuator models have been used to estimate the static load transfer between piezoelectric actuators and host structures [7-11]. The dynamic load transfer between thin-sheet actuators and an elastic host medium was recently studied using a one-dimensional actuator model [12], in which the transverse deformation of the actuator was ignored based on the assumption that the actuator has a high length-to-thickness ratio and the typical wave length is much larger than its thickness.

Piezoelectric actuator/sensor systems are being considered to use in online health monitoring of structures. Rogers [13] developed a method for identifying structure damages by measuring the mechanical impedance of structures. This method provided an effective technique for monitoring damages, which may result in measurable impedance change. System identification techniques based on modal frequency and mode shape data have also been used to identify damages [14]. To determine precisely the properties of possible damages in structures, reflected/scattering waves from damages can be used, which carry the information on the location and nature of the damages and can be measured using the attached piezoelectric sensors. This method has been used to detect cracks based on wave energy in geotechnical and geoenvironmental applications [15]. To monitor damages in structures, which are usually small in size, detailed understanding of the wave propagation is necessary. In addition, since an array of actuators/sensors are usually used, accurate estimation of the interaction between actuators/sensors becomes an important issue in the design of health monitoring systems.

The object of the present paper is to provide a comprehensive analytical study and numerical simulation of the wave propagation resulting from piezoelectric actuators bonded to or embedded in an elastic medium subjected to high frequency electric loads, based on the use of a generalized actuator model and a Pseudo-incident wave method.

ACTUATOR MODEL

Piezoelectric actuators/sensors are usually bonded to or embedded in the structure for which the health monitoring is conducted. A typical example of an elastic system under plane strain deformation with surface bonded and embedded actuators/sensors is shown in Fig. 1, which includes M thin-sheet parallel piezoceramic actuators subjected to applied electric fields. The host medium is assumed to be a homogeneous and isotropic elastic insulator. The half length and the thickness of actuator A_n are denoted a_n and h_n . The position of the centre of actuator A_n is given by (y_n^0, z_n^0) in the global coordinate (y, z) . A local coordinate system (y_n, z_n) is used to describe actuator A_n with its origin at the centre of the actuator. It is assumed that the poling direction of the actuator is along its thickness. A voltage between the upper and the lower electrodes of actuator A_n is applied, which results in an electric field of frequency ω along the poling direction, $E_z^n = (V_n^- - V_n^+)/h_n$. For the steady state response of the system, the time factor $\exp(-i\omega t)$, which applies to all the field variables, will be suppressed in this paper.

Fig. 1 The network of the actuators

Fig. 2 Actuator Model

When an electric field is applied across the electrodes attached to the two surfaces of an actuator, the actuator will be deformed in both the axial and transverse directions. This deformation will be transferred to the host medium through interfacial shear and normal stresses. Because of the continuity of deformation between the actuators and the host medium, the resulting stress field will be very complicated, especially for points near the edges of the actuator, where stress concentration will occur. It is, therefore, necessary to use simplified actuator models to simulate the load transfer between the actuator and the host medium.

For thin-sheet actuators, if the thickness is small in comparison with its length and the typical wave length of the generated elastic wave, the actuator can be regarded as a one-dimensional electromechanical element deformed in both axial and transverse directions. The interfacial normal and shear stresses transferred between the actuator and the host medium can be replaced by distributed body forces acting along the actuator, as shown in Fig. 2, in which, τ and σ_z represent the interfacial shear and normal stresses. For a surface bonded actuator, the transverse stress between the actuator and the host medium can be ignored because of the traction free condition at the upper surface of the actuator.

Based on this actuator model, the axial deformation(strain) of the actuator can be expressed in terms of the applied electric field intensity and the interfacial stresses as

$$\varepsilon_y^a(y) = \varepsilon_E(y) - \int_{-a}^y \cos k_a(\xi - y) \frac{p(\xi)}{hE_a} d\xi + \frac{\sin k_a(a + y)}{E_a \sin 2k_a a} \int_{-a}^a \cos k_a(\xi - a) p(\xi) d\xi \quad (1)$$

and the transverse stress of the actuator, $\sigma_z^a(y)$, is given by

$$\sigma_z^a(y) = \begin{cases} \sigma_E(y) + \frac{c_{31}^a \sin k_a(a + y)}{hc_{11}^a \sin 2k_a a} \int_{-a}^a p(\xi) \cos k_a(\xi - a) d\xi \\ - \frac{c_{31}^a}{hc_{11}^a} \int_{-a}^y p(\xi) \cos k_a(\xi - y) d\xi + \frac{c_{33}^a}{h} (u_z^{a+} - u_z^{a-}) & \text{embedded} \\ 0 & \text{surface bonded} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_E(y) = \frac{e_{31}^a E_z \cos k_a y}{E_a \cos k_a a}, \quad \sigma_E(y) = c_{31}^a \varepsilon_E(y) - c_{33}^a E_z$$

with

$$k_a = \omega/c_a, c_a = \sqrt{E_a/\rho_a}. \quad (3)$$

$p(y)$ is given by

$$p(y) = \begin{cases} \tau(y) + c_{31}^a \phi(y) & \text{embedded} \\ \tau(y) & \text{surface bonded} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\phi(y) = \frac{d}{dy}(u_z^{a+} - u_z^{a-}), \quad E_a = \begin{cases} c_{11}^a & \text{embedded} \\ c_{11}^a - \frac{c_{31}^a{}^2}{c_{33}^a} & \text{surface bonded} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with u_z^{a+} , u_z^{a-} being the displacements at the upper and lower surfaces of the actuator. In the above expressions, c_{11}^a , c_{31}^a , c_{33}^a , e_{31}^a , and e_{33}^a are elastic and piezoelectric constants of the actuator.

DETERMINATION OF LOAD TRANSFER

The deformation of an actuator will result in an interfacial shear stress τ and a crack-like opening ($u_z^{a+} - u_z^{a-}$) (for embedded actuator only). Correspondingly, an outgoing elastic wave propagation will be generated, which can be determined by solving an elastodynamic problem [16],

$$\varepsilon_y(y, 0)|_{matrix} = -\frac{1}{2\pi\mu} \left[\int_{-a}^a \tau(\xi) n_1(y - \xi) d\xi + \mu \int_{-a}^a \phi(\xi) n_2(y - \xi) d\xi \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_z(y, 0)|_{matrix} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\int_{-a}^a \tau(\xi) n_2(y - \xi) d\xi + \mu \int_{-a}^a \phi(\xi) n_3(y - \xi) d\xi \right] \quad (7)$$

where μ is the shear modulus of the host medium and $n_1(y)$, $n_2(y)$ and $n_3(y)$ are known functions given in Appendix A.

The crack-like opening ϕ and the shear stress τ can be determined from the continuity conditions between the actuator and the host medium, given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_y^a(y) &= \varepsilon_y(y, 0) + \varepsilon_y^I(y, 0), \\ \sigma_z^a(y) &= \sigma_z(y, 0) + \sigma_z^I(y, 0), \quad |y| < a \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\varepsilon_y(y, 0)$, $\sigma_z(y, 0)$ are the outgoing wave and the terms with superscripts ' a ' and ' I ' represent the actuator and the incident field, respectively. The continuity conditions between the actuator and the host medium can be expressed in terms of integral equations, as shown in Appendix A, which can be solved using Chebyshev polynomials,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(y) &= \sum_{j=0}^N A_j T_j(y/a) / \sqrt{1 - y^2/a^2}, \\ \phi(y) &= \sum_{j=1}^N B_j T_j(y/a) / \sqrt{1 - y^2/a^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

with T_j being the Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind and A_j and B_j being unknown constants to be determined. Accordingly, the general solution of τ and ϕ can be expressed as $2N$ linear algebraic equations, such that

$$[Q]\{c\} = \{F\} \quad (10)$$

where $\{c\} = \{A_0, A_1, \dots, A_{N-1}, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_N\}^T$ are the unknown coefficients of Chebyshev polynomial expansions. $[Q]$ and $\{F\}$ are known matrices in terms of the loading frequency, material constants and geometry of the actuator. From these equations, $\{c\}$, τ and ϕ can be obtained.

MULTIPLE ACTUATORS

For the case where multiple actuators are involved, the interaction between actuators may significantly affect the load transfer between the actuators and the host medium, and, therefore, change the resulting waveform. The interaction effect can be simulated using a newly developed Pseudo-incident wave technique.

For a specific actuator A_n , the total incident wave can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon_{ym}^I = \varepsilon_y^0 + \varepsilon_{ym}^p \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{zn}^I = \sigma_z^0 + \sigma_{zn}^p \quad (12)$$

where ε_y^0 and σ_z^0 are the mechanical incident waves due to external loading, ε_{ym}^p and σ_{zn}^p are the unknown pseudo-incident waves from other actuators. The pseudo incident field of actuator A_n can be obtained by summing up outgoing waves from all other actuators, using single actuator solutions, as

$$\varepsilon_{ym}^p = \sum_{m \neq n}^M \varepsilon_{ym}(y_n + y_n^0 - y_m^0, z_n^0 - z_m^0), \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{zn}^p = \sum_{m \neq n}^M \sigma_{zm}(y_n + y_n^0 - y_m^0, z_n^0 - z_m^0), \quad (14)$$

with $n = 1, 2, \dots, M$. Considering the consistency relation between actuators shown in (11) and (12), the following algebraic equations can be obtained,

$$[Q]^n \{c\}^n - \sum_{m \neq n}^M [R]^{mn} \{c\}^m = [f_E]^n + [R_0]^n \quad (15)$$

where $[Q]^n$, $[R]^{mn}$, $[f_E]^n$ and $[R_0]^n$ are known matrices, representing the single actuator solution, the interaction, the electric and mechanical loading.

The resulting elastodynamic field and the wave propagation in the host medium due to actuator A_n can then be obtained in terms of $\{c\}^n$ as

$$\sigma_{yy}^n(y, z) = -\frac{1}{k^2} \sum_{j=0}^N A_j^n \int_0^\infty H_1(s, z) P_j^1(s, y) ds - \frac{\mu}{k^2} \sum_{j=0}^N B_j^n \int_0^\infty H_2(s, z) P_j^1(s, y) ds \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{zz}^n(y, z) = -\frac{1}{k^2} \sum_{j=1}^N A_j^n \int_0^\infty H_3(s, z) P_j^1(s, y) ds - \frac{\mu}{k^2} \sum_{j=1}^N B_j^n \int_0^\infty H_4(s, z) P_j^1(s, y) ds \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{yz}^n(y, z) = \frac{\text{sgn}(z)}{k^2} \sum_{j=1}^N A_j^n \int_0^\infty H_5(s, z) P_j^3(s, y) ds + \frac{\text{sgn}(z)\mu}{k^2} \sum_{j=1}^N B_j^n \int_0^\infty H_6(s, z) P_j^3(s, y) ds \quad (18)$$

where k is defined in Appendix A and $P_j^1(s, y)$, $P_j^3(s, y)$, $H_1(s, z)$, $H_2(s, z)$, $H_3(s, z)$, $H_4(s, z)$, $H_5(s, z)$ and $H_6(s, z)$ are given in Appendix B. Based on this solution, the resulting wave propagation due to multiple actuators can be determined by superimposing the waves generated by different actuators.

RAYLEIGH WAVE PROPAGATION

For surface bonded actuators, because of the existence of the free surface, Rayleigh wave, which propagates along the surface, will be generated. This wave shows no delay during propagation for ideal linear elastic medium and is useful for detecting surface defects. The stress σ_{yy} carried by the Rayleigh wave due to actuator A_n can be determined from (16) as

$$\sigma_{yy}^R(y, 0) = A e^{i(s_r y + \theta)} \quad (19)$$

where A and θ are the amplitude and phase angle of the resulting Rayleigh wave, given by

$$A e^{i\theta} = \pi \sum_{j=1}^N c_j^n g_j \begin{cases} i(-1)^l & j = 2l + 1 \\ (-1)^{l+1} & j = 2l \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

with c_j^n being the Chebyshev polynomial expansion coefficients of actuator A_n , and g_j being in terms of material constants and loading frequency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will be devoted to the discussion of the dynamic electromechanical behaviour of piezoelectric actuators bonded to or embedded in an elastic medium under electric loading. Specifically, it is desired to determine the effect of different actuator parameters and the interaction between actuators upon the dynamic load transfer and the generated wave propagation in the host medium.

The material constants of the actuator are assumed to be [17],

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11}^{(a)} &= 13.9 \times 10^{10} (Pa), c_{12}^{(a)} = 6.78 \times 10^{10} (Pa), \\ c_{13}^{(a)} &= 7.43 \times 10^{10} (Pa), c_{33}^{(a)} = 11.5 \times 10^{10} (Pa), c_{44}^{(a)} = 2.56 \times 10^{10} (Pa), \\ e_{31}^{(a)} &= -5.2 (C/m^2), e_{33}^{(a)} = 15.1 (C/m^2), e_{15}^{(a)} = 12.7 (C/m^2), \\ \varepsilon_{11}^{(a)} &= 6.45 \times 10^{-9} (C/Vm), \varepsilon_{33}^{(a)} = 5.62 \times 10^{-9} (C/Vm) \\ \rho_a &= 7500 (kg/m^3) \end{aligned}$$

Dynamic Load Transfer

Figure 3 shows the normalized dynamic shear stress distribution $\tau^* = \tau/\sigma_B$, $\sigma_B = e_{33}^a E_z$ along the interface between the matrix and a surface-bonded actuator for $v = a/h = 20$, $q = \pi\mu/E_a = 0.71$ and $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$, with ρ_a and ρ_H being the mass densities of the actuator and the host medium, respectively. The loading frequency (ka) shows significant effects upon the load transfer, as evidenced by the increase of the stress level in the region of $y = 0.1a \sim 0.7a$ with increasing ka . The interfacial shear stress for an embedded actuator is depicted in Fig. 4, $\tau^* = \tau/\sigma_B$, for $v = 20$,

$q = \pi\mu/E_a = 0.46$, $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$. It should be mentioned that the effect of the loading frequency on the shear stress is much stronger for the surface-bonded actuator than that for the embedded one.

Fig. 3 The normalized interfacial shear stress

Fig. 4 The normalized interfacial shear stress

Fig. 5 shows the corresponding normalized transverse stress $\sigma_{zz}^* = \sigma_{zz}/\sigma_B$ along the interface of an embedded actuator with $\nu = 20$, $q = 0.46$, $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$. The effect of the loading frequency on the normal stress σ_{zz} is much stronger than that on the shear stress. The resulting transverse stress σ_{zz} may play an important role in generating wave propagation in the direction perpendicular to the actuator.

Fig. 5 The normalized interfacial normal stress

Fig. 6 The resulting wave propagation

The interaction between actuators may significantly change the resulting load transfer. It is found that the interfacial shear stress increases due to the interaction between collinear actuators, especially for relatively high frequencies ($ka > 3$). However, the interfacial transverse stress is not sensitive to the interaction of the actuators.

Wave Propagation

The resulting wave propagation in the host medium, which is governed by the interfacial shear and transverse stresses, is the main issue in evaluating the effectiveness of the energy transferred from the actuators to the host medium.

Fig. 7 The resulting wave propagation

Fig. 8 The resulting wave propagation

Fig. 6 shows the amplitude of the resulting elastic wave from a surface bonded actuator, $\sigma_{yy}^* = \sigma_{yy}/\sigma_B$, for the case where $ka = 3.0$, $\nu = 20$, $q = 0.71$ and $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$. High stress concentration can be observed around the tips of the actuator. The stresses will be reduced with the distance from the actuator and eventually generate a Rayleigh wave, which propagates with a constant amplitude along the surface of the matrix. Fig. 7 shows the amplitude of $\sigma_{zz}^* = \sigma_{zz}/\sigma_B$ in the elastic matrix caused by an embedded actuator for the case where $ka = 3.0$, $\nu = 20$, $q = 0.46$, $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$. Fig. 8 shows the amplitude of $\sigma_{zz}^* = \sigma_{zz}/\sigma_B$ in the matrix caused by the same embedded actuator discussed in Fig. 7 for higher frequency ($ka = 20$). A stronger wave propagation in z-direction can be observed. This is caused by the high transverse stress σ_{zz} along the actuator-matrix interface due to the high loading frequency.

Fig. 9 The resulting wave propagation

Fig. 10 The resulting wave propagation

The stresses, σ_{yy}^* , generated by two collinear actuators of the same length, is depicted in Fig. 9 for the case where $ka = 3.0$, $q = 0.71$, $\nu = 20$, $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$ and $2e = 0.5a$, with $2e$ being the distance between the actuators. Comparing with the result of the single actuator case, more complicated waveform is generated. Proper combination of the loading frequency, the size and position of the actuators is important in generating desired wave propagation. For example, for $ka = 5$, two collinear actuators with $2e = 0.5a$ will result in a Rayleigh wave with a high amplitude, which will be significantly reduced when the distance between actuators is $2e = 1.0a$. The normalized stresses $\sigma_{zz}^* = \sigma_{zz}/\sigma_B$ caused by two collinear embedded actuators of equal length is depicted in Fig. 10 for

the case where $ka = 5.0$, $v = 20$, $q = 0.46$, and $\rho_a/\rho_H = 1$. The centers of the two actuators are located at $y/a = -1.5$ and $y/a = 1.5$, respectively. Similar to the single embedded actuator cases, stronger wave propagation characterized by higher amplitude of the resulting wave in z-direction can be observed. Similar to cases involving surface-bonded actuators, different waveforms can be generated by adjusting the position and sizes of the actuators.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Analytical solution and numerical simulation are provided to study the dynamic electromechanical behaviour of piezoelectric actuators bonded to or embedded in an elastic medium under in-plane electric loads. Based upon the use of a one dimensional actuator model and a Pseudo-incident wave method, the effect of different actuator parameters and the loading frequency upon the load transfer and the resulting wave propagation are simulated and discussed.

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APPENDIX A: THE GOVERNING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS

The integral equations governing the dynamic load transfer are

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{1}{2\pi\mu} \int_{-a}^a [\tau(\xi)n_1(y-\xi) + \mu\phi(\xi)n_2(y-\xi)]d\xi \\
& \quad -\frac{\sin k_a(a+y)}{hE_a \sin 2k_a a} \int_{-a}^a p(\xi) \cos k_a(\xi-a)d\xi \\
& +\frac{1}{hE_a} \int_{-a}^y p(\xi) \cos k_a(\xi-y)d\xi = \varepsilon_E(y) - \varepsilon_y^I(y,0), \quad |y| < a \\
& -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-a}^a [\tau(\xi)n_2(y-\xi) + \mu\phi(\xi)n_3(y-\xi)]d\xi - \frac{c_{33}^a}{h} \int_{-a}^y \phi(\xi)d\xi \\
& \quad -\frac{c_{31}^a \sin k_a(a+y)}{hE_a \sin 2k_a a} \int_{-a}^a [\tau(\xi) + c_{31}^a \phi(\xi)] \cos k_a(\xi-a)d\xi \\
& +\frac{c_{31}^a}{hE_a} \int_{-a}^y [\tau(\xi) + c_{31}^a \phi(\xi)] \cos k_a(\xi-y)d\xi = \sigma_E(y) - \sigma_z^I(y,0), \quad |y| < a \text{ for embedded}
\end{aligned}$$

in which

$$n_1(y-\xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{k^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{s(s^2 - \alpha\beta)}{\alpha} \sin s(\xi-y)ds & \text{embedded} \\ \int_0^\infty \frac{2k^2 s\beta}{(2s^2 - k^2)^2 - 4s^2\alpha\beta} \sin s(\xi-y)d\xi & \text{sur face bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$n_2(y-\xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{k^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{s(-\gamma + 2\alpha\beta)}{\alpha} \sin s(\xi-y)ds & \text{embedded} \\ 0 & \text{sur face bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$n_3(y-\xi) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{k^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{(\gamma^2 - 4s^2\alpha\beta)}{s\alpha} \sin s(\xi-y)ds & \text{embedded} \\ 0 & \text{sur face bonded} \end{cases}$$

with $\gamma = s^2 + \beta^2$ and

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \sqrt{s^2 - K^2} & |s| > K \\ -i\sqrt{K^2 - s^2} & |s| < K \end{cases} \quad \beta = \begin{cases} \sqrt{s^2 - k^2} & |s| > k \\ -i\sqrt{k^2 - s^2} & |s| < k \end{cases}$$

$$K = \omega/c_L, k = \omega/c_T.$$

c_L and c_T are the longitudinal and transverse shear wave velocities of the elastic medium, respectively.

APPENDIX B: SOLUTION OF LOCAL STRESS

The functions used in equations (16)-(18) are given as

$$H_1(s, z) = \begin{cases} \frac{s(s^2 + \beta^2)}{2s\beta} e^{-\alpha|z|} - s\beta e^{-\beta|z|} & \textit{embedded} \\ \frac{2\alpha}{(2s^2 - \beta^2)^2 - 4s^2\alpha\beta} [(k^2 + 2\alpha^2)e^{-\alpha|z|} - (2s^2 - k^2)e^{-\beta|z|}] & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$H_2(s, z) = \begin{cases} -\frac{(2\alpha^2 + k^2)(s^2 + \beta^2)}{2\alpha s} e^{-\alpha|z|} + 2s\beta e^{-\beta|z|} & \textit{embedded} \\ 0 & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$H_3(s, z) = \begin{cases} -\frac{s(s^2 + \beta^2)}{2s\beta} e^{-\alpha|z|} + s\beta e^{-\beta|z|} & \textit{embedded} \\ \frac{2\alpha}{(2s^2 - \beta^2)^2 - 4s^2\alpha\beta} (2s^2 - k^2)(e^{-\alpha|z|} - e^{-\beta|z|}) & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$H_4(s, z) = \begin{cases} \frac{(s^2 + \beta^2)^2}{2\alpha s} e^{-\alpha|z|} - 2s\beta e^{-\beta|z|} & \textit{embedded} \\ 0 & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$H_5(s, z) = \begin{cases} s^2 e^{-\alpha|z|} - \frac{s^2 + \beta^2}{2} e^{-\beta|z|} & \textit{embedded} \\ \frac{4s^2\alpha\beta e^{-\alpha|z|} - (2s^2 - k^2)e^{-\beta|z|}}{(2s^2 - \beta^2)^2 - 4s^2\alpha\beta} & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$H_6(s, z) = \begin{cases} (s^2 + \beta^2)(-e^{-\alpha|z|} + e^{-\beta|z|}) & \textit{embedded} \\ 0 & \textit{surface bonded} \end{cases}$$

$$P_j^1(s, y) = J_j(sa) \begin{cases} (-1)^{n+1} \sin(sy) & j = 2n \\ (-1)^n \cos(sy) & j = 2n + 1 \end{cases}$$

$$P_j^3(s, y) = J_j(sa) \begin{cases} (-1)^n \sin(sy) & j = 2n + 1 \\ (-1)^n \cos(sy) & j = 2n \end{cases}$$